

Iodometric Microdetermination of Certain Carboxylic Acids by Potentiometric Titration Method

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Manuscript received 4 October 1982, accepted 10 August 1984

A potentiometric titration method is described for the microdetermination of certain carboxylic acids. The sample solution containing 0.01-0.1 meq of the acid is treated with an excess of potassium iodate and potassium iodide and the liberated iodine is titrated with thiosulphate potentiometrically using platinum-calomel electrode combination. The end-points obtained are sharper than those observed in the titration with alkali using glass-calomel electrode system. Further, the proposed iodometric titrations are applicable at a comparatively much lower concentrations of the acids tested. The results are accurate within 0.5%.

THE carboxyl function can be determined by titration against standard alkali using phenolphthalein as indicator. But in the microdetermination of weakly dissociated carboxylic acids the difficulties are: small inflection on the pH-neutralisation curve which progressively shortens with increasing dilution, rapid fading of the phenolphthalein colour at the end-point, and interference due to carbon dioxide¹. In the alkalimetric procedure, the content of the titration flask are boiled for a few seconds to expel the absorbed carbon dioxide. If the acid being estimated is volatile, arrangement has to be made to prevent loss due to volatilisation².

For acids that give poor titration curves in aqueous solution, a non-aqueous medium can be used. The solvent selected is protophilic so that the value of the dissociation constant of the acid in question is increased. The problem with these basic solvents is that they absorb carbon dioxide readily. Thus lithium aluminium hydride or sodium triphenylmethyl cannot be used as 0.01 N standard solution due to their extreme sensitivity to carbon dioxide, oxygen and moisture. Further, an indicator that gives sharp end-points with 0.1 N titrant might be unsatisfactory for microdeterminations using 0.01 N standard solutions³.

In the potentiometric titration of a weak acid with standard alkali using glass-calomel electrode combination, the formation of a buffer has an adverse effect on the sharpness of the end-point³. With non-aqueous solvents the potential jump near the end-point decreases with decreasing value of their dielectric constants. It has also been observed that in highly basic solvents the glass electrode does not function properly⁴.

The present communication describes an iodometric procedure for the potentiometric microdetermination of some carboxylic acids. The sample solution is treated with an excess of potassium iodate and potassium iodide followed by the poten-

tiometric titration of the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate employing platinum-calomel electrode assembly. The reactions involved are

1 ml 0.001 N thiosulphate = 0.045 mg COOH group. The end-points obtained in the proposed procedure are quite sharp even with 0.001 N thiosulphate in contrast with the acid-base titration using glass-calomel electrode combination.

Experimental

Reagents: The following solutions were prepared using A.R. grade chemicals and conductivity water: 0.0166 M (=0.1 N) potassium iodate; 5% (w/v) solution of potassium iodate; 0.1 N sodium thiosulphate standardised with potassium iodate⁴, 0.01, 0.005, 0.0016 and 0.001 N solutions prepared by dilution; 1% (w/v) fresh starch solution; 0.1 N oxalic acid, suitably diluted to obtain 0.01, 0.005, 0.0016 and 0.001 N solutions; 0.1 N sodium hydroxide prepared by titration with standard oxalic acid, and diluted to 0.01, 0.005, 0.0016 and 0.001 N; 1% (w/v) phenolphthalein solution in 1:1 ethanol-water mixture; 0.1 N carboxylic acid solutions prepared by titration with standard alkali and diluted suitably to prepare test solutions.

Apparatus: A digital pH meter having glass-calomel electrode combination and a titration potentiometer with platinum-calomel electrodes were used for performing the potentiometric titrations.

Procedure: To a sample solution (5-10 ml) containing 0.01-0.1 meq of the acid, 1 g potassium iodide and 4 ml 5% potassium iodate solution were added and the mixture was stirred by means of a magnetic stirrer. A platinum and a calomel electrode were dipped into the solution and connected to a potentiometer. Thiosulphate solution (0.001-0.01 N) was

TABLE 1—MICRODETERMINATION OF SOME AROMATIC CARBOXYACIDS BY POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION METHOD

Acid taken** mg	Iodometry			Alkalimetry		
	Found mg	Average* deviation %	Standard * deviation %	Found mg	Average * deviation %	Standard* deviation %
Benzilic						
22.824	22.842	0.08	0.13	22.842	0.08	0.20
11.412	11.421	0.08	0.20	11.469	0.50	0.55
3.804	3.810	0.16	0.26	—	—	—
2.282	2.288	0.26	0.27	—	—	—
p-Nitrobenzoic						
16.712	16.725	0.08	0.20	16.725	0.08	0.20
8.356	8.369	0.16	0.26	8.397	0.49	0.45
2.785	2.792	0.25	0.27	—	—	—
1.671	1.676	0.30	0.38	—	—	—
2,6-Dinitrobenzoic						
21.212	21.229	0.08	0.20	21.229	0.08	0.20
10.606	10.623	0.16	0.20	10.660	0.51	0.55
3.535	3.544	0.25	0.27	—	—	—
2.121	2.127	0.28	0.38	—	—	—
o-Chlorobenzoic						
15.657	15.670	0.08	0.13	15.670	0.08	0.20
7.828	7.835	0.09	0.20	7.835	0.09	0.20
2.610	2.614	0.15	0.26	—	—	—
1.565	1.569	0.26	0.27	—	—	—
Acetylsalicylic						
18.015	18.030	0.08	0.20	18.074	0.33	0.26
9.007	9.021	0.16	0.26	9.066	0.66	0.26
3.002	3.010	0.27	0.27	—	—	—
1.801	1.807	0.33	0.37	—	—	—
Phthalic						
8.300	8.306	0.07	0.13	8.368	0.80	0.26
4.150	4.153	0.07	0.20	4.201	1.22	0.27
1.383	1.385	0.14	0.26	—	—	—
0.830	0.832	0.24	0.27	—	—	—

* Calculated from six determinations.

** The 0.1 N solutions of acids prepared in 1 : 1 water-ethanol and diluted to obtain test solutions. Due to poor solubility of phthalic acid 0.025 N solution was prepared and suitably diluted.

periodically added through a microburette. After each addition, the solution was stirred and potentiometer reading recorded. The end-point was located by plotting the volume of the titrant added vs $\Delta E/\Delta V$, and a sharp peak in the graph indicated the end-point. ΔE is the change in potential resulting from the addition of ΔV , a definite volume of the titrant.

The thiosulphate solution was standardised potentiometrically with standard oxalic acid solution by the same procedure described above for titrating the sample solution. The concentration of oxalic acid solution, used for standardising thiosulphate, should be comparable to the acid present in the sample solution.

Results and Discussion

The proposed iodometric procedure was applied to the microdetermination of some carboxylic acids of different nature. The potentiometric titrations were performed at four concentration levels, the

amounts of acids taken being 0.01-0.1 meq. The results are recorded in Table 1. The recovery studies show that the average deviation is between 0.2-0.5%, whereas the standard deviation is in the range 0.2-0.4%.

The titrimetry of a carboxylic acid with a strong base does not yield accurate results when the acid content of the sample is 0.05 meq⁵ or less owing to a drawn-out indistinct end-point. In performing a potentiometric titration with glass-calomel electrodes, the potential jump at the end-point is about 30 mV/0.1 ml of 0.01 N sodium hydroxide as the titrant. This potential jump progressively decreases with the dilution of the titrant and the sample solution. When a sample containing about 0.025 meq acid is titrated with 0.0025 N alkali, the potential jump in the vicinity of the equivalence-point is very small and a series of equal jumps is observed so that the end-point cannot be located as shown in Table 1.

The proposed method involves the addition of an excess of potassium iodate and potassium iodide

to the sample solution and subsequent potentiometric titration of the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate using platinum-calomel electrodes combination. By carrying out a large number of preliminary experiments it was concluded that by adding 4 ml 5% potassium iodate and 1 g potassium iodide to sample solutions containing 0.01-0.1 meq of acids, the quantitative liberation of iodine could be accomplished. The potentiometric titration required 15-20 min which is enough for the completion of the reaction, hence, it is not necessary to allow time before starting the titration. The potential jump at

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration of 10 ml of 0.001 N *p*-nitrobenzoic acid. Curve (I) obtained by the proposed iodometric method and (II) by acid-base potentiometry.

the end-point was found to be 60-100 mV/0.1 ml of 0.001-0.01 N thiosulphate titrant. Fig. 1 shows the potentiometric titration curves obtained by titrating 10 ml of 0.001 N nitrobenzoic acid with 0.001 N sodium hydroxide and iodometric titration with 0.001 N thiosulphate.

The proposed method does not require any special reagents and experimental conditions are not critical. The end-point is quite sharp even with samples containing 0.01 meq acid. Hence, the iodometric method is quite suitable for determining carboxylic acids tested, at micro level. The added advantage of the method is that it can be applied to estimate acid content in those samples which contain a component capable of reacting with alkali⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Fellowship to one of them (R.S.).

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